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Review Article

Effect Of Active Constituents of Garlic on Cardiovascular Disorders

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ABSTRACT

Garlic and its preparations have been extensively recognized as medicines for the prevention and treatment of cardiovascular and other metabolic illnesses, diabetes, hypertension, thrombosis, atherosclerosis, and hyperlipidemia. Garlic's therapeutic value in cardiovascular diseases was more hopeful in experimental studies, which provoked several clinical trials. Many clinical trials show a favorable impact on practically all of the cardiovascular problems previously listed; nevertheless, some unfavorable studies have recently raised doubts about the effectiveness of garlic, particularly its ability to decrease cholesterol. As the least expensive method of preventing cardiovascular disease, using garlic properly to reap its full benefits is a major problem for experts worldwide. World. This review is a little attempt to make a connection between experimental and clinical studies and to discuss the possible mechanisms of such therapeutic actions of garlic.

INTRODUCTION

Dietary variables are important in the development of many human diseases, including cardiovascular disease. Diets high in fruits, herbs, and spices are linked to a lower risk of cardiovascular disease, according to epidemiological research. Garlic established a reputation over generations as a horrible preventative and therapeutic medicinal ingredient in the traditions of many civilizations. Because garlic is used medicinally all over the world and because it is widely believed to help prevent sickness and boost vitality, it has garnered

special attention in modern medicine. Nowadays garlic preparations and extract have been shown to have numerous positive experimental and clinical benefits. The majority of research has linked these biological reactions to i) lowering the risk of cardiovascular and cancer disorders, and ii) boosting immunological function. iii) Improved detoxification of foreign compound, iv) hepatoprotection, v) antimicrobial and antioxidant effect. This article provides an overview of the effectiveness of garlic in treating illnesses other than cardiovascular disease.

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Historical Perspective of Garlic

It's amazing to see how societies who were never in contact with one another evolved to the same beliefs regarding the use of garlic in health care disease and health. It may teach us valuable lessons if folk knowledge is not ignored. Sumerian clay tablets from 2600–2100 BC provide some of the earliest records of this culinary herb and medicine. According to the medical treatise *Codex Ebers* (published before 1550 BC), garlic was considered a significant medicinal herb by the ancient Egyptians, particularly for those engaged in hard labor. [1,2]. There is evidence that during the first Olympics in Greece, athletes were given garlic to help them become more stamina-efficient. [1]. Garlic was prescribed as a remedy for respiration and digestion, mostly in cases of diarrhea and worm infestation in traditional Chinese medicine [3]. Garlic was widely used in the ancient Indian medical systems of Tibbi, Unani, and Auryveda as a key component of the healing power of plants. [2]. Garlic has long been used to cure heart disease and arthritis, according to the renowned Indian ancient medical treatise *Charaka-Samhita*. Garlic was used to treat leprosy, tiredness, and parasite diseases. *Bower Manuscript*, a different ancient Indian medical treatise (c. 300 AD), [4]. As a new era began, Europe began to pay more attention to the medicinal application of garlic. Pietro Mattiali, a renowned physician from Siena in the sixteenth century, recommended garlic to treat kidney problems, worm infestations, and digestive issues, and to support mothers going through difficult childbirths [2]. Garlic was used to treat plague, dropsy, constipation, and toothaches in England. [4]. Researchers have been attempting to verify several garlic characteristics, particularly in identifying the active therapeutic components, and mechanisms of action and exploring the probable benefits as food supplements modern era.

Atheroscleand Lipid Metabolism

Atherosclerosis is a multifarious disease characterized by an excessive inflammatory, fibro-fatty, proliferative response to artery wall damage involving several cell types, like smooth muscle cells, monocyte-derived macrophages, T-lymphocytes, and platelets [7]. Hyperlipidemia constitutes a most importantetiopathologicalaspect for atherosclerosis. The medicinal significance of garlic is best known to prevent atherosclerosis. Garlic's medical value is mostly recognized for its ability to decrease cholesterol and prevent atherosclerosis.

Human Studies

Since 1975, there have been more than 46 human studies (found via a Medline search) examining the potential of garlic and garlic products to decrease cholesterol. These studies, in hyperlipidemic patients, were mostly placebo-controlled, double-blind, and randomized using garlic powder instead of raw garlic for 4–16 weeks. These trials show a significant reduction in serum triglycerides and cholesterol. Of these investigations, only around one-third measured lipoproteins, where significant favorable changes in LDL-cholesterol levels (11–26% decrease) were consistently observed. Very few examinations using garlic powder (with low allicin yields) were unsuccessful in demonstrating any effects on lipid levels [24,25]. Regarding the hypolipidemic impact of garlic, eighteen clinical research have been published in the previous ten years (1993–2002). Out of nine studies, all revealed poor outcomes, with seven of these investigations utilizing garlic powder. Shows the result as specified in Table- 1(Table-1) [26-34]. Additional variables could be the study's length, diet restrictions, way of life, and cholesterol analysis techniques [35, 36].

Table 1
Studies Showing No Cholesterol-Lowering Effect:

References	Preparation	Duration	Dose
Ziaei et al., 2001 [26]	Garlic powder (Garlet)	3 months	800 mg/day
Gardner et al., 2001 [27]	Garlic powder	12 weeks	500, 1000 mg/day
Rahman et al., 2000 [28]	Aged garlic extract	13 weeks	5 ml/day
Superko et al., 2000 [29]	Garlic powder	3 months	900 mg/day
Byrne et al., 1999 [30]	Garlic powder (Kwai)	6 months	900 mg/day
McCordle et al., 1998 [31]	Garlic powder (Kwai)	8 weeks	900 mg/kg
Berthold et al., 1998 [32]	Steam-distilled garlic oil	12 weeks	10 mg/day
Isaacsohn et al., 1998 [33]	Garlic powder (Kwai)	12 weeks	900 mg/day
Simons et al., 1995 [34]	Garlic powder (Kwai)	12 weeks	900 mg/day
Luley et al., 1986 [25]	Commercial dried garlic	6 weeks	600 mg/day
Lutomski, 1984 [24]	Commercial garlic preparation	12 weeks	—

Possible Mechanism/s

Garlic's ability to lower cholesterol content in artery walls has been linked to its preventive impact against atherosclerosis. Garlic has direct antiatherogenic (preventive) and antiatherosclerotic (causing regression) actions at the arterial wall level. [39]. the hepatic activity of cholesterogenic and lipogenic enzymes, including 3-hydroxy-3- methyl-glutaryl-CoA (HMG CoA) reductase, fatty acid synthase, malic enzyme, and glucose-6 phosphate dehydrogenase was depressed by garlic [40]. The increased production of acidic and neutral steroids following garlic consumption indicates the excretion of cholesterol feeding, was increased by Garlic [20]. Aqueous garlic extract [42] and LDL removed from people who received AGE [41] were discovered to have a noticeably higher oxidation resistance. These

findings suggest that reduced LDL oxidation may be one of the potent mechanisms accounting for garlic's advantages in atherosclerosis. [43]. At first, allicin was shown to be the active ingredient with antiatherosclerotic activity. However, recent in vitro research has shown that water-soluble organosulfur compounds—particularly S-allyl cysteine (SAC) found in old garlic extract and diallyl-di-sulfur (DADS) found in garlic oil—are also highly effective at inhibiting the formation of cholesterol. [40,4]

Fibrinolytic Activity

Insufficiency of the relevant components or suppression of fibrinolytic activity (FA) could throw off the hemostatic equilibrium and permit an excessive build-up of fibrin. Disturbance in the

coagulation-fibrinolytic system could be a significant contributing factor to the development of ischemia and thrombosis in diabetes, hypertension, hypercholesterolemia, and other conditions. Therefore, the antithrombotic action is more favorable the higher the FA. The time required for euglobulin lysis usually determines FA. Patients with acute or elderly myocardial infarctions died while their plasma fibrinogen, euglobulin lysis time, and antiplasmin values were at their greatest infarction. This suggests that prediction in Part of what causes myocardial infarction is the extent to which plasma fibrinolysis is impaired [45].

Human Studies

Every human study on garlic's fibrinolytic action has demonstrated its beneficial effects (Table – (Table –2).2. Both short-term and long-term consumption of raw garlic and garlic improved Fibrinolytic activity (FA) was improved by. Bordia first, in 1975, demonstrated that Garlic oil

enhanced FA three hours after administration. According to Bordia, chronic (3 weeks to 3 months) treatment of garlic oil (dose: equivalent to 1 gm/kg of fresh garlic) significantly raises FA in both acute myocardial infarction patients and healthy individuals, ranging from 36% to 130%. [49-52]. The same results are also found in some other investigators [53-55]. Moreover, dried garlic powder has been experienced for its fibrinolytic activity. Two studies [24,25] showed no distinction [56] showed Tissue plasminogen activator activity following consumption of both acute and long-term garlic powder as well as increased FA. Frying removes the strong acrid aroma of garlic but conserves its useful properties on FA. The rise in FA, It is noted that garlic has a quick start of action and that the effect lasts for as long as the garlic is consumed within six hours after administration. Bordia Rescently (1998) discovered that consuming an ethyl acetate extract for three months compressed raw garlic also increased FA [57].

Table 2
Fibrinolytic Activity in Humans:

References	Preparation	Duration	Effect
Bordia et al., 1975 [46]	Essential garlic oil	Acute effect	Increased FA
Bordia et al., 1977 [10]	Essential garlic oil	3 months	Increased FA
Bordia et al., 1978 [50]	Essential garlic oil	20 days	Increased FA
Bordia et al., 1978 [58]	Essential garlic oil	3 months	Increased FA
Chutani and Bordia, 1981 [52]	Fresh and fried garlic	acute effect and 4 weeks	Increased FA

References	Preparation	Duration	Effect
Arora and Arora, 1981 [54]	Essential garlic oil	Acute effect	Slightly increased FA
Arora et al., 1981 [55]	Essential garlic oil	12 weeks	Increased FA only after 4 weeks
Bordia et al., 1982 [51]	Essential garlic oil	3 weeks	Increased FA
Lutomski, 1984 [24]	Dried garlic powder	12 weeks	No increase in FA

Luley et al., 1986 [25]	Dried garlic powder	6 weeks	No increase in FA
Legnani et al., 1993 [56]	Dried garlic powder	Acute and 14 days	Increased FA
Bordia et al., 1998 [57]	Ethyl acetate extract of garlic	3 months	Increased FA

Platelet aggregation

Obstruction of blood flow results in thromboembolic diseases and myocardial infarction. It is simply called platelet activation. ADP and thrombin Platelet aggregation which is superimposed, an antecedent incidence on an artery with atherosclerosis causing total are also responsible for platelet activation. These activated platelets change shape, put out pseudopodia, discharge their granules, and adhere to other platelets, initiating the process of platelet aggregation. Aggregation is fostered by a cytokine secreted by neutrophils, platelet activating factors (PAF), monocytes, and platelets [59]. The conclusion is that garlic has great potential to inhibit platelet aggregation.

Human Study

Studies conducted on humans have shown that garlic elicits a favorable reaction. Garlic also improves fibrinolysis and platelet adhesion or aggregation in humans. (Table- (Table-3).3). The dose-dependent reduction in platelet aggregation by garlic is first shown by Bordia (1978) [72]. Inhibition of In vitro platelet aggregation triggered by arachidonate, calcium ionophore, collagen, epinephrine, and ADP [57,61,73-75] is shown by Garlic oil, raw garlic, and other forms of garlic extract. Inhibition of platelet aggregation is also due to regular consumption of garlic powder and garlic oil [28,50,55,76-79].

Table 3
Inhibition of Platelet aggregation (PA) in humans:

References	Preparations	Duration	Effect
[72 Bordia, 1978]	Garlic	In-vitro	Dose-dependent Platelet aggregation
Vanderhock et al., 1980 [73]	Garlic oil	In vitro	Inhibit PA
Boullin, 1981 [80]	Fresh garlic	Single Dose	Inhibit PA
Ariga et al., 1981 [85]	Methyl allyl trisulfide	In vitro	Inhibit PA
Arora and Arora, 1981 [54]	Ether extract of garlic	Single Dose	Increased coagulation time
Bordia et al., 1982 [51]	Ether extract of garlic	3 weeks	Inhibit PA
Samson, 1982 [76]	Essential garlic oil	10 days	No PA activity
Apitz-Castro et al., 1983 [74]	Garlic extract and 3 pure component	In vitro	Inhibit PA

References	Preparations	Duration	Effect
Block et al., 1984 [86]	Ajoene	In vitro	Inhibit PA
Srivastava, 1984 [61]	Aqueous extract of garlic	In vitro	Inhibit PA

Srivastava, 1986 [75]	Aqueous extract of garlic	In vitro	Inhibit PA
Harenberg et al., 1988 [77]	Dried garlic powder	4 weeks	No PA activity
Kiesewetter et al., 1991 [78]	Garlic powder	4 weeks	Inhibit PA
Kiesewetter et al., 1993 [87]	Garlic powder	4 weeks	Inhibit PA
Legnani et al., 1993 [56]	Garlic powder	Single Dose and 14 days	Inhibit PA
Morris et al., 1995 [88]	Oil extract (equivalent to 15 gm of raw garlic)	In-vitro and in vivo (5 days)	Inhibit PA in in-vitro No in-vivo PA activity
Bordia et al., 1998 [57]	Ethyl acetate extract of garlic	In-vitro study	Inhibit PA
Sreiner and Lin, 1998 [79]	Aged garlic extract	10 months	Inhibit PA
Rahman and Billington, 2000 [28]	Aged garlic extract	13 weeks	Inhibit PA
Steiner and Li, 2001 [89]	Aged garlic extract	6 weeks	Dose-dependent inhibition of PA

References	Preparation	Duration	Effect
Bordia et al., 1978 [50]	Essential garlic oil	20 days	Increased FA
Bordia et al., 1978 [58]	Essential garlic oil	3 month	Increased FA
Chutani and Bordia, 1981 [52]	Fresh and fried garlic	acute effect and 4 weeks	Increased FA
Arora and Arora, 1981 [54]	Essential garlic oil	Acute effect	Slightly increased FA
Arora et al., 1981 [55]	Essential garlic oil	12 weeks	Increased FA only after 4 weeks
Bordia et al., 1982 [51]	Essential garlic oil	3 weeks	Increased FA
Lutomski, 1984 [24]	Dried garlic powder	12 weeks	No increase in FA
Luley et al., 1986 [25]	Dried garlic powder	6 weeks	No increase in FA
Legnani et al., 1993 [56]	Dried garlic powder	Acute and 14 days	Increased FA
Bordia et al., 1998 [57]	Ethyl acetate extract of garlic	3 months	Increased FA

Possible Mechanism/s

The antiplatelet mechanism of garlic is often more predictable than its other biological effects. The thromboxane formation inhibits the results of

lipooxygenase and phospholipase activity produced in platelets is reduced by garlic. These effects give details about the inhibition of platelet aggregation. As garlic inhibits aggregation caused by calcium ionophore A23187, it is suggested that the

antiaggregation effect is possible because of intraplatelet enlistment of calcium. Inhibiting Garlic extract may have inhibited epinephrine-induced aggregation, decreasing cytosolic calcium concentrations via facilitating calcium uptake into platelets [75]. Studies by Jamaluddin et al. (1988) [84] show that ajoene interacts with a purified hemoprotein linked to platelet activation. The hemoprotein's binding to ligands is thought to be physiologically significant as efGarlic extract may have inhibited epinephrine- induced aggregation, decreasing cytosolic calcium concentrations via facilitating calcium uptake into platelets [75]. Studies by Jamaluddin et al. (1988) [84] show that ajoene interacts with a purified hemoprotein linked to platelet activation. The hemoprotein's binding to ligands is thought to be physiologically significant as effects modified by Ajoene. Allicin reduces the aggregation of platelets but does not change the action of vascular prostacyclin synthase. It blocks ionophore A23187-stimulated human neutrophil lysosomal enzyme release. For this purpose, garlic shows important components and its effects at various steps involved in the process of platelet aggregation.

Animal Studies

Garlic extracts administered intravenously to experimental animals caused modest decreases in both the diastolic and systolic blood pressure [91, 92]. Dogs' blood pressure has been shown to drop dramatically for a few hours after an intragastric

dosage (as low as 2.5 mg/kg b.wt) of garlic powder) was administered [94]. According to other animal trials conducted on rats and dogs, garlic has a 'normalizing' impact on raised blood pressure [93, 95-98]. Garlic's antihypertensive effect has been shown time and time again in various research. The antihypertensive properties of allicin, a significant component of garlic, were also investigated. In hypertensive rats, long-term oral allicin therapy reduced blood pressure [99, 100]. In a rat's isolated lung, allicin also produced pulmonary vasodilatation [101]. In the '2 kidney 1-clip' model of rat hypertension, single and multiple doses of aqueous garlic extract decreased prostaglandin E2 and thromboxane B2, which in turn decreased hypertension [102]. , garlic also reduced endothelin-1-induced contraction in a dose-dependent manner, in isolated rat pulmonary arteries [103].

Human Research

The capacity of garlic to lessen blood pressure in people is shown in Table 4.4. Garlic's hypotensive properties were identified by Leoper and DeBray in 1921 [106]. Damrau (1941) examined previous research, as well as his studies on 26 cases [107]. An average loss in systolic (SBP) blood pressure of 12.3 mm Hg and diastolic (DBP) blood pressure of 6.5 mm Hg, a decrease in blood pressure was noted in 85% of the patients. Higher than 25% of the participants had an SBP decline of 20 millimeters of mercury or Hg or higher.

Table 4
Blood pressure lowering effect in Humans:

References	Preparation	Duration	Dose	Effect
Ziaei et al., 2001 [26]	Garlic tablet (Garlet)	3 months	800 mg/day	↓ hypertension
Qidwai, 2000 [115]	Garlic in diet	Chronic intake	134 gm/month	↓ SBP
McC Crindle et al., 1998 [31]	Kwai	8 weeks	900 mg/day	No changes

Steiner et al., 1996 [116]	Aged garlic extract	6 months	7.2 gm/day	↓ SBP & DBP
Simons et al., 1995 [34]	Kwai	12 weeks	900 mg/day	No changes
Jain et al., 1993 [117]	Kwai	12 weeks	900 mg/day	No changes
Mcmahan& Vargas, 1993 [118]	Garlic powder	Acute	2400 mg	↓ BP
Kiesewetter et al., 1991 [78]	Garlic powder	4 weeks	800 mg/day	↓ DBP
Auer et al., 1990 [119]	Kwai	12 weeks	600 mg/day	↓ SBP & DBP
Zimmerman et al., 1990 [120]	Kwai	3 weeks	900 mg/day	No changes
Vorberg et al., 1990 [121]	Kwai	16 weeks	900 mg/kg	↓ SBP & DBP
Piotrowski, 1948 [108]	Alcoholic extract of garlic	1 week	0.6–1.2 gm/day	↓ SBP

Among the first clinical trials in which patients with hypertension received garlic under carefully monitored conditions were examined by Piotrowski (1948) [108]. Within a week of starting administration of 0.6–1.2 g of a dialyzed, alcoholic garlic extract, two-fifths of the 100 patients showed a 20 mm Hg or higher drop in SBP. Research using dried garlic powder (Kwai tablets) revealed that taking 0.6 g of garlic powder daily could lower blood pressure by approximately 9% on average [77,109]. Additionally, a randomized double-blind trial showed that garlic had a positive effect on blood pressure and blood lipids in mildly hypertensive participants [110]. According to those reports, garlic may be helpful in the management of mild hypertension. Pektov (1979) references numerous research papers, predominantly from Bulgaria and the Soviet Union. Showing that the qualities of garlic and its compounds include lowering blood pressure. These findings also suggest an improvement in how patients feel, along with a noticeable decrease in terms of systolic blood pressure (SBP), by 20–30 mm Hg and diastolic blood pressure (DBP) by 10–20 mm Hg. Additionally, a study conducted in

China in 1986 with 70 individuals with high blood pressure, who were administered 50 grams of garlic oil of raw garlic daily, found that 47 of them experienced a significant to moderate decrease in their blood pressure levels. Neil and Silagy conducted just one meta-analysis. (1994) [113]. Eight trials that were particularly carried out in hypertensive participants were all identified using the same method. Three of the seven trials evaluating the effect of garlic vs a placebo demonstrated a statistically significant decrease in systolic blood pressure (SBP), and four in diastolic blood pressure (DBP). Participants treated with garlic had a higher overall pooled mean difference in the absolute change (from baseline to final measurement) of SBP than participants treated with a placebo. The equivalent decrease in the patients treated with garlic was marginally less for DBP. "Garlic powder preparation may Be of some clinical use in subjects with mild hypertension," according to this meta-analysis. However, It is currently not supported by enough data to be advised as a standard clinical treatment for hypertensive patients. Firm conclusions require

further trials that are carefully planned, assessed, and conducted.

Possible Mechanism/S

Rashid and Khan (1985) suggested that the mechanism of the antihypertensive effect of garlic is through a prostaglandin-like effect that reduces peripheral vascular resistance (92). Gamma-glutamylcysteine is a compound found because garlic has the potential to inhibit the angiotensin-converting enzyme in vitro, which may reduce blood pressure (114). Garlic may protect against hypoxic pulmonary disease because it alters the synthesis and activity of endothelium-derived relaxing and constricting components. Vasoconstriction. [103] Garlic induces nitric oxide-dependent relaxation of pulmonary arteries. This hypothesis is explained by the fact that the NOS inhibitor NG-nitro-L-arginine methyl ester (L-NAME) blocks the vasodilatory action of garlic [103,104]. However, another study showed that the pulmonary vasodilatory action of allicin is independent of NO synthesis, ATP-sensitive

channels (K⁺), and activation of cyclooxygenase enzymes (101).

Human Studies

Aortic stiffening is a valid surrogate marker for clinical endpoints such as myocardial infarction and cerebrovascular accident, and it is also a significant cardiovascular risk factor for morbidity and mortality. High systolic blood pressure, elevated pulse pressure with increased ventricular afterload, decreased subendocardial blood flow, and increased pulsatile stress in the peripheral arteries are all caused by elevated aortic stiffness [154]. Long-term garlic consumption has been shown to attenuate the increase in aortic stiffness with aging in the population. This implies a preventive influence on the aorta's elastic characteristics associated with human aging [155]. This study demonstrated that regular long-term consumption of garlic powder shielded endothelial cells, additionally from oxidative damage. [155]. Patients with found that a 12-week course of therapy with 800 mg/day of garlic powder was effective.

Table 5
Direct cardioprotective effect of garlic in Humans:

References	Preparation	Duration	Dose	Effect
Li et al., 2000 [137]	Garlicin	10 days	64 mg/day i.v. drip	↓ Unstable angina
Breithaupt-Grogler et al., 1997 [155]	Garlic powder	7 years	300 mg/day	↑ the elastic property of blood vessels
Kiesewetter et al; 1993 [87]	Garlic powder	12 weeks	800 mg/day	↓ peripheral arterial occlusive disease
Kiesewetter et al., 1991 [78]	Garlic powder	4 weeks	800 mg/day	↓ plasma viscosity
Jung et al., 1991 [157]	Garlic powder	Single dose	900 mg/day	↓ plasma viscosity & ↑ skin perfusion
Kiesewetter et al; 1990 [156]	Garlic powder	Acute	–	↑ capillary perfusion

Adverse Effects

We take it due to its longstanding use as a mainstay in our diet, we take it for granted that garlic is safe in a range of dosages. Countless years. However, a few rare

reports draw attention to some of the harmful and poisonous effects of garlic. Human investigation Clinical trials employing garlic and the preparations therefore revealed relatively few side effects. The

majority of side effects that were reported were vague. The most common complaints were nausea and digestive discomfort [170]. According to a survey conducted by Koch (1995), there were there were 39 articles. Between 1938 and 1994 that detailed reactions to garlic allergies. [171]. The majority of these instances comprised allergic contact dermatitis, which has been linked to occupational exposure to allergens and can occasionally be severe [172] which has been documented in individuals who have been exposed to garlic at work. Additionally, there have been isolated reports of allergic rhinitis, conjunctivitis, or bronchospasms brought on by ingesting or inhaling garlic [173,174]. Bloating, headaches, dizziness, and excessive perspiration were among other side effects that were reported [170]. Fresh garlic with garlic powder may interact negatively interacting with platelet aggregation or anticoagulant aggregation inhibitors, potentially causing a potentially fatal bleeding episode [175 – 179].

CONCLUSION

Garlic consumption is inversely correlated with a lower chance of cardiovascular disease progression, according to epidemiological research [180–182]. The idea that eating garlic has a major cardioprotective effect is supported by a large body of research, including studies on both humans and animals. However, some aspects of using garlic correctly, such as using the various preparations that are available, the dosage, the length of time it takes, and how it interacts with generic medications, need to be optimized. To pinpoint the precise compounds in garlic or garlic-derived products that account for the majority of its biological effects, more research needs to be done.

REFERENCES

1. Lawson LD. Garlic: a review of its medicinal effects and indicated active compounds. In: Lawson LD & Bauer R, editor. *Phytomedicines of Europe. Chemistry and Biological Activity. Series 691.* American Chemical Society, Washington, DC; 1998. pp. 176–209
2. Moyers S. *Garlic in Health, History, and World Cuisine.* Suncoast Press, St Petersburg, FL. 1996. pp. 1–36.
3. Woodward PW. *Garlic and Friends: The History, Growth and Use of Edible Alliums.* Hyland House, Melbourne, Australia. 1996. pp. 2–22.
4. Rivlin RS. Patient with hyperlipidemia who received garlic supplements. *Lipid management. Report from the Lipid Education Council.* 1998; 3:6–7
5. Borek C. Antioxidant health effect of aged garlic extract. *J Nutr.* 2001; 131:1010S–1015S.
6. Ryu K, Ide N, Matsuura H, Itakura Y. N alpha-(1-deoxy-D-fructos-1-yl)-L-arginine, an antioxidant compound identified in aged garlic extract. *J Nutr.* 2001; 131:972S–976S.
7. Schwartz CJ, Valente AJ, Sprague EA. A modern view of atherogenesis. *Am J Cardiol.* 1993; 71:9b–14b.
8. Jain RC. Onion and garlic an experimental cholesterol atherosclerosis in rabbits. *Artery.* 1975; 1:115–125.
9. Jain RC. Effect of garlic on serum lipids, coagulability, and fibrinolytic activity of blood. *Am J Clin Nutr.* 1977; 30:1380–1381.
10. Bordia A, Verma SK, Vyas AK, Khabya BL, Rathore AS, Bhu N, Bedi HK. Effect of essential oil of onion and garlic on experimental atherosclerosis in rabbits. *Atherosclerosis.* 1977; 26:379–386.
11. Chang MLW, Johnson MA. Effect of garlic on carbohydrate metabolism and lipid synthesis in rats. *J Nutr.* 1980; 110:931–936
12. Kamanna VS, Chandrasekhara N. Hypocholesterolemic activity of different fractions of garlic. *Ind J Medical Res.* 1984; 79:580–583.
13. Mand JK, Gupta PP, Soni GL, Singh R. Effect of garlic on experimental atherosclerosis in rabbits. *Ind Heart J.* 1985; 37:183–188.

14. Betz E, Weidler R. Die Wirkung von Knoblauchextrakt auf die atherosclerose bei Kaninchen. In: Betz E, editor. Die anwendung aktueller Methoden in der Arteriosklerose. Forschung. 1989. pp. 304–311.
15. Rajasree CR, Rajmohan T, Agusti KT. Biochemical effects of garlic on lipid metabolism in alcohol-fed rats. *Ind J Exp Biol.* 1999; 37:243–247.
16. Mathew BC, Daniel RS. Hypolipidemic effect of garlic protein substituted for casein diet of rats compared to those of garlic oil. *Ind J Exp Biol.* 1996; 34:337–340.
17. Qureshi AA, Din ZZ, Abuirameileh N, Burger WC, Ahmed Y, Elson CE. Suppression of avian hepatic lipid metabolism by solvent extracts of garlic: impact on serum lipids. *J Nutr.* 1983; 113:1746–1755.
18. Kamanna VS, Chandrasekhara N. Effect of garlic on serum lipoproteins cholesterol levels in albino rats rendered hypercholesteremic by feeding cholesterol. *Lipids.* 1982; 17:483–488.
19. Chi MS. Effect of garlic products on lipid metabolism in cholesterol-fed rats. *Proc Soc Exp Biol Med.* 1982; 171:174–178.
20. Chi MS, Koh ET, Stewart TJ. Effect of garlic on lipid metabolism in rats fed cholesterol or lard. *J Nutr.* 1982; 112:241–248.
21. Abramovitz D, Gavri S, Harats D, Levkovitz H, Mirelman D, Miron T, Eilat-Adar S, Rabinkov A, Wilchek M, Eldar M, Vered Z. Allicin-induced decrease in the formation of fatty streaks (atherosclerosis) in mice fed a cholesterol-rich diet. *Coron Artery Dis.* 1999; 10:515–519.
22. Efendy JL, Simmons DL, Campbell GR, Campbell JH. The effect of the aged garlic extract, 'Kyolic', on the development of experimental atherosclerosis. *Atherosclerosis.* 1997; 132:37–42.
23. Campbell JH, Efendy JL, Smith NJ, Campbell GR. Molecular basis by which garlic suppresses atherosclerosis. *J Nutr.* 2001; 131:1006S–1009S.
24. Lutomski J. Klinische Untersuchungen zur therapeutischen Wirksamkeit von Ilyarogiffknoblauchpillen mit Rutin. *Z Phytotherapia.* 1984; 5:938–942.
25. Luley C, Lehmann-Leo W, Moller B, Martin T, Schwartzkopff W. Lack of the efficacy of dried garlic in patients with hyperlipoproteinemia. *Arzneimittelforschung / Drug Res.* 1986; 36:766–768.
26. Ziaei S, Hantoshzadeh S, Rezasoltani P, Lamyian M. The effect of garlic tablet on plasma lipids and platelet aggregation in nulliparous pregnant at high risk of preeclampsia. *Eur J Obstet Gynecol Reprod Biol.* 2001; 99:201–206.
27. Gardner CD, Chatterjee LM, Carlson JJ. The effect of a garlic preparation on plasma lipid levels in moderately hypercholesterolemic adults. *Atherosclerosis.* 2001; 154:213–220.
28. Rahman K, Billington D. Dietary supplementation with aged garlic extract inhibits ADP-induced platelet aggregation in humans. *J Nutr.* 2000; 130:2662–2665.
29. Superko HR, Krauss RM. Garlic powder, effect on plasma lipids, postprandial lipemia, low-density lipoprotein particle size, high-density lipoprotein subclass distribution, and lipoprotein (a). *J Am Coll Cardiol.* 2000; 35:321–326.
30. Byrne DJ, Neil HA, Vallance DT, Winder AF. A pilot study of garlic consumption shows no significant effect on markers of oxidation or sub-fraction composition of low-density lipoprotein including lipoprotein (a) after allowance for non-compliance and the

- placebo effect. *Clin Chim Acta*. 1999; 285:21–33.
31. McCrindle BW, Helden E, Conner WT. Garlic extract therapy in children with hypercholesterolemia. *Arch PediatrAdolesc Med*. 1998; 152:1089–1094.
 32. Berthold HK, Sudhop T. Garlic preparations for prevention of atherosclerosis. *Curr OpinLipidol*. 1998; 9:565– 569.
 33. Isaacsohn JL, Moser M, Stein EA, Dudley K, Davey JA, Liskov E, Black HR. Garlic powder and plasma lipids and lipoproteins: a multicenter, randomized, placebo-controlled trial. *Arch Intern Med*. 1998; 158:1189–1194.
 34. Simons LA, Balasubramanian S, Von Konigsmark M, Parfitt A, Simons J, Peters W. On the effects of garlic on plasma lipids and lipoproteins in mild hypercholesterolemia. *Atherosclerosis*. 1995; 113:219–225.
 35. Silagy C, Neil A. Garlic as a lipid-lowering agent meta-analysis. *J R Coll Physician Lond*. 1994; 28:39–45. [PMC free article]
 36. Warshafsky S, Kamer RS, Sivak SL. Effect of garlic on total serum cholesterol, a meta-analysis. *Ann Intern Med*. 1993; 119:599–605.
 37. Neil HA, Silagy CA, Lancaster T, Hodgeman J, Vos K, Moore JW, Jones L, Cahill J, Fowler GH. Garlic powder in the treatment of moderate hyperlipidemia: a controlled trial and meta-analysis. *J R Coll Physicians Lond*. 1996; 30:329–334. [PMC free article]
 38. Stevinson C, Pittler MH, Ernst E. Garlic for treating hypercholesterolemia. A meta-analysis of randomized clinical trials. *Ann Intern Med*. 2000; 133:420–429.
 39. Orekhov AN, Grunwald J. Effects of garlic on atherosclerosis. *Nutrition*. 1997; 13:656–663
 40. Yu-Yan Yeh, Liu L. Cholesterol-lowering effect of garlic extracts and organosulfur compounds: Human and animal studies. *J Nutr*. 2001; 131:989S–993S.
 41. Munday JS, James KA, Fray LM, Kirkwood SW, Thompson KG. Daily supplementation with aged garlic extract, but not raw garlic, protects low-density lipoprotein against in vitro oxidation. *Atherosclerosis*. 1999; 143:399–404.
 42. Lewin G, Popov I. Antioxidant effects of aqueous garlic extract. 2nd communication: Inhibition of the Cu (2+)- initiated oxidation of low-density lipoproteins. *Arzneimittelforschung*. 1994; 44:604–607.
 43. Lau Benjamin HS. Suppression of LDL oxidation by garlic. *J Nutr*. 2001; 131:958S–988S.
 44. Gebhardt R, Beck H. Differential inhibitory effects of garlic-derived organosulfur compounds on cholesterol biosynthesis in primary rat hepatocyte culture. *Lipids*. 1996; 31:1269–1276.
 45. Rodger B, Roberty B, Edward S. Fibrinolytic activity in acute myocardial infarction. *Am J Clin Pathol*. 1972; 57:359–363.
 46. Bordia A, Arora SK, Kothari LK, Jain KC, Rathore BS, Rathore AS, Dube MK, Bhu N. The protective action of essential oils of onion and garlic in cholesterol-fed rabbits. *Atherosclerosis*. 1975; 22:103–109.
 47. Sainani GS, Desai DB, Natu MN, Katrodia KM, Valame VP, Sainani PG. Onion, garlic, and experimental atherosclerosis. *Jpn Heart J*. 1979; 20:351–357.
 48. Mirhadi SA, Singh S, Gupta PP. Effect of garlic supplementation to cholesterol-rich diet on the development of atherosclerosis in rabbits. *Ind J Exp Biol*. 1991; 29:162–168.
 49. Bordia AK, Joshi HK, Sandhya YK, Bhu N. Effect of essential oil of garlic on serum fibrinolytic activity in patients with coronary artery disease. *Atherosclerosis*. 1977; 28:155.

50. Bordia AK, Sodhya SK, Rathore AS, Bhu N. Essential oil of garlic on blood lipids and fibrinolytic activity in patients with coronary artery disease. *J Assoc Phys Ind.* 1978; 26:327–33.
51. Bordia AK, Sharma KD, Parmar VK, Varma SK. Protective effect of garlic oil on the changes produced by 3 weeks of fatty diet on serum cholesterol serum triglycerides, fibrinolytic activity, and platelet adhesiveness in man. *Ind Heart J.* 1982; 34:86.
52. Chutani SK, Bardia A. The effect of fried versus Raw garlic on fibrinolytic activity in man. *Atherosclerosis.* 1988; 38:417–421.
53. Sainani GS, Desai DB, Gorha NH, Natu SM, Pise DV, Sainani PG. Effect of dietary garlic and onion on serum lipid profile in Jain Community. *Ind J of Med Res.* 1979; 69:776–780.
54. Arora RC, Arora S. Comparative effects of clofibrate, garlic, and onion on alimentary hyperlipemia. *Atherosclerosis.* 1981; 39:447–452.
55. Arora RC, Arora S, Gupta RK. The long-term use of garlic in ischemic heart disease. *Atherosclerosis.* 1981; 40:175–179.
56. Legnani C, Frascaro M, Guazzaloca G, Ludovici S, Cesarano G, Coccheri S. Effects of a dried garlic preparation on fibrinolysis and platelet aggregation in healthy subjects. *Arzneimittelforschung.* 1993; 43:119–122.
57. Bordia A, Verma SK, Srivastava KC. Effect of garlic (*Allium sativum*) on blood lipids, blood sugar, fibrinogen, and fibrinolytic activity in patients with coronary artery disease. *Prostaglandins Leukot Essent Fatty Acids.* 1998; 58:257–263.
58. Bordia AK, Joshi HK. Garlic on fibrinolytic activity in cases of acute myocardial infarction. *J Assoc Physiol Ind.* 1978; 26:323–326.
59. Harfenist WJ, Murry RK, Murry RK, Mayes PA, Grannen DK, Rodwell VW. Plasma proteins, immunoglobulin, and clotting factors. In: Barnes DA, editor. *Harper's Biochemistry.* 25. McGraw-Hill, New York, A Lange Medical Book; 2000. pp. 737–762.
60. Ali M, Thomson M, Alnaqeeb MA, al-Hassan JM, Khater SH, Gomes A. Antithrombotic activity of garlic: its inhibition of the synthesis of thromboxane-B₂ during infusion of arachidonic acid and collagen in rabbits. *Prostaglandins Leukot Essent Fatty Acids.* 1990; 41:95–99.
61. Srivastava KC. Effects of aqueous extracts of onion, garlic, and ginger on platelet aggregation and metabolism of arachidonic acid in the blood
62. Ali M. Mechanism by which garlic (*Allium sativum*) inhibits cyclooxygenase activity. Effect of raw versus boiled garlic extract on the synthesis of prostanoids. *Prostaglandins Leukot Essent Fatty Acids.* 1995; 53:397–400.
63. Ali M, Bordia T, Mustafa T. Effect of raw versus boiled aqueous extract of garlic and onion on platelet aggregation. *Prostaglandins Leukot Essent Fatty Acids.* 1999; 60:43–47
64. Laurence WVD, John DF. Garlic extract prevents acute platelet thrombus formation in stenosed canine coronary arteries. *Am Heart J.* 1989; 117:973–975.
65. Thomson M, Mustafa M, Ali M. Thromboxane-B₂ levels in serum of rabbits receiving a single intravenous dose of aqueous extract of garlic and onion. *Prostaglandins Leukot Essent Fatty Acids.* 2000; 63:217–221.
66. el-Sabban F, Fahim MA, Radwan GM, Zaghoul SS, and Singh S. Garlic preserves patency and delays hyperthermia-induced thrombosis in pial microcirculation. *Int J Hyperthermia.* 1996; 12:513–525.

67. el-Sabban F, Radwan GM. Influence of garlic compared to aspirin on induced photothrombosis in mouse pial microvessels, in vivo. *Thromb Res.* 1997; 88:193–203.
68. Apitz-Castro R, Escalante J, Vargas R, Jain MK. Ajoene, the antiplatelet principle of garlic, synergistically potentiates the antiaggregatory action of prostacyclin, forskolin, indomethacin, and dipyridamole on human platelets. *Thromb Res.* 1986; 42:303–311.
69. Apitz-Castro R, Badimon JJ, Badimon L. A garlic derivative, ajoene, inhibits platelet deposition on severely damaged vessel walls in an in vivo porcine experimental model. *Thromb Res.* 1994; 75:243–249.
70. Apitz-Castro R, Badimon JJ, Badimon L. Effect of ajoene, the major antiplatelet compound from garlic, on platelet thrombus formation. *Thromb Res.* 1992; 68:145–155.
71. Makheja AN, Bailey JM. Antiplatelet constituents of garlic and onion. *Agents Actions.* 1990; 29:360–363. Bordia A. Effect of garlic on human platelet aggregation in vitro. *Atherosclerosis.* 1978; 30:355–360.
72. Vanderhock JY, Makheja AN, Bailey JM. Inhibition of fatty acid oxygenases by onion and garlic acts. Evidence for the mechanism by which these oils inhibit platelet aggregation. *Biochem Pharmacol.* 1980; 29:3169–3173.
73. Apitz-Castro R, Cabrera S, Cruz MR, Ledezma E, Jain MK. Effects of garlic extract and three pure components isolated from it on human platelet aggregation, arachidonate metabolism, release activity, and platelet ultrastructure. *Thromb Res.* 1983; 32:155–169.
74. Srivastava KC. Evidence for the mechanism by which garlic inhibits platelet aggregation. *Prostaglandin Leukot Med.* 1986; 22:313–321.
75. Samson RR. Effects of dietary garlic and temporal drift on platelet aggregation. *Atherosclerosis.* 1982; 44:119–120.
76. Harenberg J, Giese C, Zimmermann R. Effect of dried garlic on blood coagulation, fibrinolysis, platelet aggregation, and serum cholesterol levels in patients with hyperlipoproteinemia. *Atherosclerosis.* 1988; 74:247–249.
77. Kiesewetter H, Jung F, Pindur G, Jung EM, Mrowietz C, Wenzel E. Effect of garlic on thrombocyte aggregation, microcirculation, and other risk factors. *Int J Clin Pharmacol Ther Toxicol.* 1991; 29:151–155.
78. Steiner M, Lin RS. Changes in platelet function and susceptibility of lipoproteins to oxidation associated with administration of aged garlic extract. *J Cardiovasc Pharmacol.* 1998; 31:904–908.
79. Boullin DJ. Garlic as a platelet inhibitor. *Lancet.* 1981; 1:776–777.
80. Wagner H, Wierer M, Fessler B. Effects of garlic constituents on arachidonate metabolism. *Planta Med.* 1987; 53:305–306.
81. Srivastava KC, Tyagi OD. Effects of a garlic-derived principle (ajoene) on aggregation and arachidonic acid metabolism in human blood platelets. *Prostaglandins Leukot Essent Fatty Acids.* 1993; 49:587–595.
82. Apitz-Castro R, Ledezma E, Escalante J, Jain MK. The molecular basis of the antiplatelet action of ajoene: direct interaction with the fibrinogen receptor. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun.* 1986; 141:145–150.
83. Jamaluddin MP, Krishnan LK, Thomas A. Ajoene inhibition of platelet aggregation: possible mediation by a hemoprotein. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun.* 1988; 153:479–486.
84. Ariga T, Oshiba S, Tamada T. Platelet aggregation inhibitor in garlic. *Lancet.* 1981; 1:150–151.

85. Block E, Ahmad S, Jain MK, Crecely RW, Apitz Castro R, Cruz MR. (E, Z) Ajoene: A potent antithrombic agent from garlic. *J Amer Chem Soc.* 1984; 106:8295–8296.
86. Kiesewetter H, Jung F, Jung EM, Mroweitz C, Koscielny J, Wenzel E. Effect of garlic on platelet aggregation in patients with increased risk of juvenile ischaemic attack. *Eur J Clin Pharmacol.* 1993; 45:333–336.
87. Morris J, Burke V, Mori TA, Vandongen R, Beilin LJ. Effects of garlic extract on platelet aggregation: a randomized placebo-controlled double-blind study. *Clin Exp Pharmacol Physiol.* 1995; 22:414–417.
88. Steiner M, Li W. Aged garlic extract, a modulator of cardiovascular risk factors: a dose-finding study on the effects of AGE on platelet functions. *J Nutr.* 2001; 131:980S–984S.
89. Schulz V, Hansel R, Tyler VE. *Rational Phytotherapy; Physicians' guide to herbal medicine.* Springer-verlag, Berlin; 2001. Cardiovascular system. pp. 107–168.
90. Sial AY, Ahmed SJ. Study of the hypotensive action of garlic extract in experimental animals. *J Pak Med Assoc.* 1982; 32:237–239.
91. Rashid A, Khan HH. The mechanism of hypotensive effect of garlic extract. *J Pak Med Assoc.* 1985; 35:357–362.
92. Chanderkar AG, Jain PK. Analysis of hypotensive action of *Allium sativum* (garlic) *Ind J Physiol Pharmacol.* 1973; 17:132–133.
93. Pantoja CV, Chiang Ch L, Norris BC, Concha JB. Diuretic, natriuretic, and hypotensive effects produced by *Allium sativum* (garlic) in anesthetized dogs. *J Ethnopharmacol.* 1991; 31:325–331.
94. Banerjee AK. Effect of aqueous extract of garlic on arterial blood pressure of normotensive and hypertensive rats. *Artery.* 1976; 2:369.
95. Ruffin J, Hunter SA. An evaluation of the side effects of garlic as an antihypertensive agent. *Cytobias.* 1983; 37:85–89.
96. Foushee DB, Ruffin J, Banerjee U. Garlic as a natural agent for the treatment of hypertension: A preliminary report. *Cytobios.* 1982; 34:145–152.
97. Malik ZA, Siddiqui S. Hypotensive effect of freeze-dried garlic (*Allium sativum*) sap in the dog. *J Pak Med Assoc.* 1981; 31:12–13.
98. Elkayam A, Mirelman D, Peleg E, Wilchek M, Miron T, Rabinkov A, Sadetzki S, Rosenthal T. The effects of allicin and enalapril in fructose-induced hyperinsulinemic hyperlipidemic hypertensive rats. *Am J Hypertens.* 2001; 14:377–381.
99. Ali M, Al-Qattan KK, Al-Enezi F, Khanafer RM, Mustafa T. Effect of allicin from garlic powder on serum lipids and blood pressure in rats fed with a high cholesterol diet. *Prostaglandins Leukot Essent Fatty Acids.* 2000; 62:253–259.
100. Kaye AD, De Witt BJ, Anwar M, Smith DE, Feng CJ, Kadowitz PJ, Nossaman BD. Analysis of responses of garlic derivatives in the pulmonary vascular bed of the rat. *J Appl Physiol.* 2000; 89:353–358.
101. Al-Qattan KK, Khan I, Alnaqeeb MA, Ali M. Thromboxane-B₂, prostaglandin-E₂ and hypertension in the rat 2-kidney 1-clip model: a possible mechanism of the garlic induced hypotension. *Prostaglandins Leukot Essent Fatty Acids.* 2001; 64:5–10.
102. Kim-Park S, Ku DD. Garlic elicits a nitric oxide-dependent relaxation and inhibits hypoxic pulmonary vasoconstriction in rats. *Clin Exp Pharmacol Physiol.* 2000; 27:780–786.
103. Fallon MB, Abrams GA, Abdel-Razek TT, Dai J, Chen SJ, Chen YF, Luo B, Oparil S, and Ku DD. Garlic prevents hypoxic

- pulmonary hypertension in rats. *Am J Physiol.* 1998; 275:L283–L287.
104. Brandle M, al Makdessi S, Weber RK, Dietz K, Jacob R. Prolongation of life span in hypertensive rats by dietary interventions. Effects of garlic and linseed oil. *Basic Res Cardiol.* 1997; 92:223–232.
105. Leoper M, DeBray M. Hypotensive effect of tincture of garlic.
106. Damru F. The use of garlic concentrate in vascular hypertension. *Med Rec.* 1941; 153:249–251.
107. Piotrowski'ail en GL. therapeutique. *Praxis.* 1948; 26:488–492.
108. Konig FK, Scineider B. Knoblauch bessert Durch-blutungstorungenArztliche Praxis. 1986. pp. 44–35.
109. Auer W, Eiber A, Hertkom E, Kohrle U, Lenz A, Mader F, Merx W, Otto G, Schmid-Oto B, benheim H. Hypertonie and Hyperlipidamie: In leichterenauch Knoblauch. *Der Allgemeinarzi.* 1989; 3:205–208.
110. Petkov V. Plants and hypotensive, antiatheromatous and coronarodilatating action: *Am J Chin Med.* 1979; 7:197–236.
111. Zhejiang Institute of Traditional Chinese Medicine The effect of essential oil of garlic on hyperlipemia and platelet aggregation – an analysis of 308 cases. Cooperative Group for Essential Oil of Garlic. *J Tradit Chin Med.* 1986; 6:117–120.
112. Silagy CA, Neil HA. A meta-analysis of the effect of garlic on blood pressure. *J Hyperten.* 1994; 12:463–468.
113. Sendl A, Elbl G, Steinke B, Redl K, Breu W, Wagner H. Comparative pharmacological investigations of *Allium ursinum* and *Allium sativum*. *Planta Medica.* 1992; 58:1–7.
114. Qidwai W, Qureshi R, Hasan SN, Azam SI. Effect of dietary garlic (*Allium Sativum*) on the blood pressure in humans – a pilot study. *J Pak Med Assoc.* 2000; 50:204–207.
115. Steiner M, Khan AH, Holbert D, Lin RI. A double-blind crossover study in moderately hypercholesterolemic men compared the effect of aged garlic extract and placebo administration on blood lipids. *Am J Clin Nutr.* 1996; 64:866–870.
116. Jain AK, Vargas R, Gotzkowsky S, McMahan FG. Can garlic reduce levels of serum lipids? A controlled clinical study. *Am J Med.* 1993; 94:632–635?
117. McMahan FG, Vargas R. Can garlic lower blood pressure? A pilot study. *Pharmacotherapy.* 1993; 13:406–407.
118. Auer W, Eiber A, Hertkom E, Kohrle U, Lenz A, Mader F, Merx W, Otto G, Schmid-Oto B, benheim H. Hypertonie and Hyperlipidamie: In leichterenauch Knoblauch. *Der Allgemeinarzi.* 1989; 3:205–208.
119. Zimmermann W, Zimmermann B. Reduction in elevated blood lipids in hospitalized patients by a standardized garlic preparation. *Br J Clin Prac.* 1990; 44:20–23.
120. Vorberg G, Schneider B. Therapy with garlic: results of a placebo-controlled, double-blind study. *Br J Clin Prac.* 1990; 44:7–11.
121. Granner DK, Murry RK, Mayes PA, Grannen DK, Rodwell VW. Hormones of the pancreas and gastrointestinaltract. In: Barnes DA, editor. *Harper's Biochemistry.* 25. McGraw-Hill, New York, A Lange Medical Book; 2000. pp.610–626.
122. Ohaeri OC. Effect of garlic oil on the levels of various enzymes in the serum and tissue of streptozotocin- diabeticrats. *Biosci Rep.* 2001; 21:19–24.
123. Patumraj S, Tewit S, Amatyakul S, Jariyapongskul A, Maneesri S, Kasantikul V, Shepro D. Comparative effects of garlic and aspirin on diabetic cardiovascular complications. *Drug Deliv.* 2000; 7:91–96.
124. Swanston-Flatt SK, Day C, Bailey CJ, Flatt PR. Traditional plant treatments for diabetes.

- Studies in normal and streptozotocin diabetic mice. *Diabetologia*. 1990; 33:462–464.
125. Farva D, Goji LA, Joseph PK, Augusti KT. Effects of garlic oil on streptozotocin-diabetic rats maintained on normal and high-fat diets. *Indian J Biochem Biophys*. 1986; 23:24–27.
126. Kumar GR, Reddy KP. Reduced nociceptive responses in mice with alloxan-induced hyperglycemia after garlic (*Allium sativum*) treatment. *Indian J Exp Biol*. 1999; 37:662–666.
127. Augusti KT, Sheela CG. Antiperoxide effect of S-allyl cysteine sulfoxide, an insulin secretagogue, in diabetic rats. *Experientia*. 1996; 52:115–120.
128. Sheela CG, Kumud K, Augusti KT. Anti-diabetic effect of onion and garlic sulfoxide amino acids in rats. *Planta Medica*. 1995; 61:356–357.
129. Sheela CG, Augusti KT. Antidiabetic effects of S-allyl cysteine sulphoxide isolated from garlic *Allium sativum* Linn. *Indian J Exp Biol*. 1992; 30:523–526.
130. Jain RC, Vyas CR. Garlic in alloxan-induced diabetic rabbits. *Am J Clin Nutr*. 1975; 28:684–685.
131. Mathew PT, Augusti KT. Studies on the effect of allicin (diallyl disulfide-oxide) on alloxan diabetes I. Hypoglycaemic action and enhancement of serum insulin effect and glycogen synthesis. *Indian J Biochem Biophys*. 1973; 10:209–212.
132. Kasuga S, Ushijima M, Morihara N, Itakura Y, Nakata Y. Effect of aged garlic extract (AGE) on hyperglycemia induced by immobilization stress in mice. *Nippon Yakurigaku Zasshi*. 1999; 114:191–197.
133. Jain RC, Vyas CR. Hypoglycemic action of onion and garlic. *Lancet*. 1973; 2:1491.
134. Zhang XH, Lowe D, Giles P, Fell S, Connock MJ, Maslin DJ. Gender may affect the action of garlic oil on the plasma cholesterol and glucose levels of normal subjects. *J Nutr*. 2001; 131:1471–1478.
135. Ali M, Thomson M. Consumption of garlic clove a day could be beneficial in preventing thrombosis. *Prostaglandins Leukot Essent Fatty acids*. 1995; 53:211–212.
136. Li G, Shi Z, Jia H, Ju J, Wang X, Xia Z, Qin L, Ge C, Xu Y, Cheng L, Chen P, Yuan G. A clinical investigation on garlic injection for treatment of unstable angina pectoris and its actions on plasma endothelin and blood sugar levels. *J Tradit Chin Med*. 2000; 20:243–246.
137. Rietz B, Belagyi J, Torok B, Jacob R. The radical scavenging ability of garlic examined in various models. *Bolletino Chimico Farmaceutico*. 1995; 134:69–76.
138. Martin N, Bardisa L, Pantojaa C, Vargas M, Quezaada P, Valenzuela J. Antiarrhythmic profile of a garlic dialystate assay in dogs and isolated atrial preparations. *J Ethnopharmacol*. 1994; 43:1–8.
139. Martin N, Bardisa L, Pantojaa C, Vargas M, Quezaada P, Valenzuela J. Antiarrhythmic profile of a garlic dialystate assay in dogs and isolated atrial preparations. *J Ethnopharmacol*. 1994; 43:1–8.
140. Aqel MB, Gharaibah MN, Salhab AS. Direct relaxant effects of garlic juice on smooth and cardiac muscles. *J Ethnopharmacol*. 1991; 33:13–19.
141. Tongia SK. Effects of intravenous garlic Juice *Allium sativum* on rat Electrocardiogram. *Ind J Physiol Pharmacol*. 1984; 28:250–252.
142. Banerjee SK, Maulik M, Manchanda SC, Dinda AK, Gupta SK, Maulik SK. Dose-dependent induction of endogenous antioxidants in rat heart by chronic administration of garlic. *Life Sciences*. 2002; 70:1509–1518.
143. Banerjee SK, Maulik M, Manchanda SC, Dinda AK, Das TK, Maulik SK. Garlic-induced alteration in rat liver and kidney

- morphology and associated changes in endogenous antioxidant status. *Food Chem Toxicol.* 2001; 39:793–797.
144. Imai J, Ide N, Nagae S, Moriguchi T, Matsuura H, Itakura Y. Antioxidant and radical scavenging effects of aged garlic extract and its constituents. *Planta Med.* 1994; 60:417–420.
145. Geng Z, Lau B. Aged garlic extract modulates glutathione redox cycle and superoxide dismutase activity in vascular endothelial cells. *Phytother Res.* 1997; 11:54–56.
146. Wei Z, Lau BHA. Garlic inhibits free radical generation and augments antioxidant enzyme activity in vascular endothelial cells. *Nutr Res.* 1998; 18:61–70.
147. Banerjee SK, Maulik M, Gupta SK, Manchanda SC, Dinda AK, Maulik SK. Effect of chronic garlic intake on endogenous antioxidants and ischemic-reperfusion injury in isolated rat heart. *Ind J Pharmacol.* 2001; 33:298.
148. Mukherjee S, Maulik M, Talwar KK, Dinda AK, and Maulik SK. Effect of chronic raw garlic administration in Adriamycin induced oxidant stress in rat hearts. *Ind J Pharmacol.* 2001; 33:297.
149. Kojima R, Epstein CJ, Mizui T, Carlson E, Chaqn PH. Protective effects of aged garlic extracts on doxorubicin-induced cardiotoxicity in the mouse. *Nutr Cancer.* 1994; 22:163–173.
150. Ciplea AG, Richter KD. The protective effect of *Allium sativum* and *crataegus* on isoprenaline-induced tissue necrosis in rats. *Arzneim-Forsch / Drug Res.* 1988; 38:1583–1592.
151. Isensee H, Rietz B, Jacob R. Cardioprotective action of garlic (*Allium sativum*). *Arzneim Forsch / Drug Res.* 1993; 43:94–98.
152. Yamasaki T, Lau BH. Garlic compounds protect vascular endothelial cells from oxidant injury. *Nippon YakurigakuZasshi.* 1997; 110:138P–141P.
153. Breithaupt-Grogler K, Belz GG. Epidemiology of the arterial stiffness. *Pathol Biol (Paris)* 1999; 47:604–613.
154. Breithaupt-Grogler K, Ling M, Boudoulas H, Belz GG. Protective effect of chronic garlic intake on elastic properties of aorta in the elderly. *Circulation.* 1997; 96:2649–2655.
155. Kiesewetter H, Jung F, Mrowietz C, Pindur G, Heiden M, Wenzel E, Gu LD. Effects of garlic on blood fluidity and fibrinolytic activity: a randomized, placebo-controlled, double-blind study. *Br J Clin Pract.* 1990; 69:24–29.
156. Jung EM, Jung F, Mrowietz C, Kiesewetter H, Pindur G, Wenzel E. Influence of garlic powder on cutaneous microcirculation. A randomized placebo-controlled double-blind cross-over study in apparently healthy subjects. *Arzneimittelforschung.* 1991; 41:626–630.
157. Das T, Roychoudhury A, Sharma A, Talukder G. Effects of crude garlic extract on mouse chromosomes in vivo. *Food and Chemical Toxicology.* 1996; 34:43–47.
158. Augusti KT. Therapeutic values of onion (*Allium cepa* L) and garlic (*Allium sativum* L). *Ind J Exp Biol.* 1996; 34:634–640.
159. Nakagawa S, Masamoto K, Sumiyoshi H, Kunihiro K, Fuwa T. Effect of raw and extracted aged garlic on growth of young rats and their organ after peroral administration. *J Toxicol Sci.* 1980; 5:91–112.
160. Joseph PK, Rao KR, Sundaresh CS. Toxic effects of garlic extract and garlic oil in rats. *Ind J Exp Biol.* 1989; 27:977–979.
161. Chen L, Hong JY, So E, Hussain AH, Cheng WF. Decrease of hepatic catalase level by treatment with diallyl sulfide and garlic homogenates in rats and mice. *J Biochem Mol Toxicol.* 1999; 13:127–133.

162. Augusti KT, Mathew PT. Effect of allicin on certain enzymes of the liver after a short-term feeding to normal rats. *Experientia*. 1975; 31:148–149.
163. Dixit VP, Joshi S. Effects of chronic administration of garlic (*Allium sativum* Linn) on testicular function. *Ind J Exp Biol*. 1982; 20:534–536.
164. Egen-Schwind C, Eckard R, Kemper FH. Metabolism of garlic constituents in the isolated perfused rat liver. *Planta Medica*. 1992; 58:301–305.
165. Sheen LY, Li CK, Sheu SF, Meng RHC, Tsai SJ. Effect of the active principle of garlic-diallyl sulfide- on cell viability, detoxification capability, and the antioxidation system on primary rat hepatocytes. *Food Chem Toxicol*. 1996; 34:971–978.
166. Sheen LY, Chen HW, Kung YL, Liu CT, Lii CK. Effects of garlic oil and its organosulfur compounds on the activities of hepatic drug-metabolizing and antioxidant enzymes in rats fed high- and low-fat diets. *Nutr Cancer*. 1999; 35:160–166.
167. Gallwitz H, Bonse S, Martinez-Cruz A, Schlichting I, Schumacher K, Krauth-Siege RL. Ajoene is an inhibitor and subversive substrate of human glutathione reductase and *Trypanosoma cruzi* trypanothione reductase: crystallographic, kinetic, and spectroscopic studies. *J Med Chem*. 1999; 42:364–372.
168. Rabinkov A, Miron T, Mirelman D, Wilchek M, Glozman S, Yavin E, and Weiner L. S-Allylmercaptogluthathione: the reaction product of allicin with glutathione possesses SH-modifying and antioxidant properties. *Biochim Biophys Acta*. 2000; 1499:144–153.
169. Beck E, Grunwald J. *Allium sativum* in der Stufentherapie der Hyperlipidämie. *Med Welt*. 1993; 44:516–520.
170. Koch HP, Hahn G, Lawson L, Reuter HD, Siegers CP. Garlic introduction to the therapeutic application of *Allium sativum* L. Williams & Wilkins, Baltimore, im Druck. 1995.
171. Eming SA, Piontek JO, Hunzelmann N, Rasokat H, Scharffetter-Kachanek K. Severe toxic contact dermatitis caused by garlic. *Br J Dermatol*. 1999; 141:391–392.
172. Falleroni AE, Zeiss CR, Levitz D. Occupational asthma secondary to inhalation of garlic dust. *J Allergy Clin Immunol*. 1981; 68:156–160.
173. Papageogiou D, Corbet JP, Menezes F-Brando, Pecegueiro M, and Benezra C. Allergic: contact dermatitis to garlic (*Allium sativum* L) identification of the allergens: the role of mono-, di- and trisulfides present in garlic. *Arch Dermatol Res*. 1983; 275:229–234.
174. Rose KD, Croissant PD, Parliament CF, Levin MB. Spontaneous Spinal Epidural Hematoma with Associated Platelet Dysfunction from Excessive Garlic Ingestion: A Case Report. *Neurosurgery*. 1990; 26:880–882.
175. Sunter WH. Warfarin and garlic. *Pharm J*. 1991; 246:722.
176. Burnham BE. Garlic is a possible risk for postoperative bleeding. *Plast Recon Surg*. 1995; 95:213.
177. Fugh-Berman A. Herb-drug interactions. *Lancet*. 2000; 355:134–138.
178. Petry JJ. Garlic and postoperative bleeding. *Plastic Recon Surg*. 1995; 96:483–484.
179. Kandler BS. Garlic (*Allium sativum*) and onion (*Allium cepa*): a review of their relationship to cardiovascular disease. *Prev Med*. 1987; 16:670–685.
180. Keys A. Wine, garlic, and CHD in seven countries. *Lancet*. 1980; 1:145–146.
181. Lawson LD. Garlic: a review of its medicinal effects and indicated active compounds. In: Lawson LD & Bauer R, editor.

- Phytomedicines of Europe. Chemistry and Biological Activity. Series 691. American Chemical Society, Washington, DC; 1998. pp. 176–209.
182. Moyers S. Garlic in Health, History, and World Cuisine. Suncoast Press, St Petersburg, FL. 1996. pp. 1–36. Woodward PW. Garlic and Friends: The History, Growth and Use of Edible Alliums. Hyland House, Melbourne, Australia. 1996. pp. 2–22.
183. Rivlin RS. Patient with hyperlipidemia who received garlic supplements. Lipid management. Report from the Lipid Education Council. 1998; 3:6–7.
184. Borek C. Antioxidant health effect of aged garlic extract. *J Nutr.* 2001; 131:1010S–1015S.
185. Ryu K, Ide N, Matsuura H, Itakura Y. N alpha-(1-deoxy-D-fructos-1-yl)-L-arginine, an antioxidant compound identified in aged garlic extract. *J Nutr.* 2001; 131:972S–976S.
186. Schwartz CJ, Valente AJ, Sprague EA. A modern view of atherogenesis. *Am J Cardiol.* 1993; 71:9b–14b.
187. Jain RC. Onion and garlic an experimental cholesterol atherosclerosis in rabbits. *Artery.* 1975; 1:115–12. Betz E, Weidler R. Die Wirkung von Knoblauchextrakt auf die Atherogenese bei Kaninchen. In: Betz E, editor. Die Anwendung aktueller Methoden in der Arteriosklerose. Forschung. 1989. pp. 304–311.]
188. Chang MLW, Johnson MA. Effect of garlic on carbohydrate metabolism and lipid synthesis in rats. *J Nutr.* 1980; 110:931–936.
189. Rajasree CR, Rajmohan T, Agusti KT. Biochemical effects of garlic on lipid metabolism in alcohol-fed rats. *Ind J Exp Biol.* 1999; 37:243–247.
190. Chi MS, Koh ET, Stewart TJ. Effect of garlic on lipid metabolism in rats fed cholesterol or lard. *J Nutr.* 1982; 112:241–248.
191. Abramovitz D, Gavri S, Harats D, Levkovitz H, Mirelman D, Miron T, Eilat-Adar S, Rabinkov A, Wilchek M, Eldar M, Vered Z. Allicin-induced decrease in the formation of fatty streaks (atherosclerosis) in mice fed a cholesterol-rich diet. *Coron Artery Dis.* 1999; 10:515–519.
192. Efendy JL, Simmons DL, Campbell GR, Campbell JH. The effect of the aged garlic extract, 'Kyolic', on the development of experimental atherosclerosis. *Atherosclerosis.* 1997; 132:37–42.
193. Campbell JH, Efendy JL, Smith NJ, Campbell GR. Molecular basis by which garlic suppresses atherosclerosis. *J Nutr.* 2001; 131:1006S–1009S.
194. Lutomski J. Klinische Untersuchungen zur therapeutischen Wirksamkeit von llyarogiffknoblanchpillen mit Rutin. *Z Phytotherapia.* 1984; 5:938–942.
195. Luley C, Lehmann-Leo W, Moller B, Martin T, Schwartzkopff W. Lack of the efficacy of dried garlic in patients with hyperlipoproteinemia. *Arzneimittelforschung / Drug Res.* 1986; 36:766–768.
196. Ziaei S, Hantoshzadeh S, Rezasoltani P, Lamyian M. The effect of garlic tablet on plasma lipids and platelet aggregation in nulliparous pregnant at high risk of preeclampsia. *Eur J Obstet Gynecol Reprod Biol.* 2001; 99:201–206.
197. Simons LA, Balasubramanian S. Von Konigsmark M, Parfitt A, Simons J, Peters W. On the effects of garlic on plasma lipids and lipoproteins in mild hypercholesterolemia. *Atherosclerosis.* 1995; 113:219–225.
198. Silagy C, Neil A. Garlic as a lipid-lowering agent meta-analysis. *J R Coll Physician Lond.* 1994; 28:39–45. Warshafsky S, Kamer RS, Sivak SL. Effect of garlic on total serum cholesterol, a meta-analysis. *Ann Intern Med.* 1993; 119:599–605.

199. Gardner CD, Chatterjee LM, Carlson JJ. The effect of a garlic preparation on plasma lipid levels in moderately hypercholesterolemic adults. *Atherosclerosis*. 2001; 154:213–220.
200. Rahman K, Billington D. Dietary supplementation with aged garlic extract inhibits ADP-induced platelet aggregation in humans. *J Nutr*. 2000; 130:2662–2665.
201. Superko HR, Krauss RM. Garlic powder, effect on plasma lipids, postprandial lipemia, low-density lipoprotein particle size, high-density lipoprotein subclass distribution, and lipoprotein (a). *J Am Coll Cardiol*. 2000; 35:321–326.
202. Byrne DJ, Neil HA, Vallance DT, Winder AF. A pilot study of garlic consumption shows no significant effect on markers of oxidation or sub-fraction composition of low-density lipoprotein including lipoprotein (a) after allowance for non-compliance and the placebo effect. *Clin Chim Acta*. 1999; 285:21–33.
203. McCrindle BW, Helden E, Conner WT. Garlic extract therapy in children with hypercholesterolemia. *Arch Pediatr Adolesc Med*. 1998; 152:1089–1094.
204. Berthold HK, Sudhop T. Garlic preparations for prevention of atherosclerosis. *Curr Opin Lipidol*. 1998; 9:565–569. Isaacsohn JL, Moser M, Stein EA, Dudley K, Davey JA, Liskov E, Black HR. Garlic powder and plasma lipids and lipoproteins: a multicenter, randomized, placebo-controlled trial. *Arch Intern Med*. 1998; 158:1189–1194.
205. Stevinson C, Pittler MH, Ernst E. Garlic for treating hypercholesterolemia. A meta-analysis of randomized clinical trials. *Ann Intern Med*. 2000; 133:420–429.
206. Neil HA, Silagy CA, Lancaster T, Hodgeman J, Vos K, Moore JW, Jones L, Cahill J, Fowler GH. Garlic powder in the treatment of moderate hyperlipidemia: a controlled trial and meta-analysis. *J R Coll Physicians Lond*. 1996; 30:329–334.
207. Orekhov AN, Grunwald J. Effects of garlic on atherosclerosis. *Nutrition*. 1997; 13:656–663.
208. Yu-Yan Yeh, Liu L. Cholesterol-lowering effect of garlic extracts and organosulfur compounds: Human and animal studies. *J Nutr*. 2001; 131:989S–993S.
209. Munday JS, James KA, Fray LM, Kirkwood SW, Thompson KG. Daily supplementation with aged garlic extract, but not raw garlic, protects low-density lipoprotein against in vitro oxidation. *Atherosclerosis*. 1999; 143:399–404. Lewin G, Popov I. Antioxidant effects of aqueous garlic extract. 2nd communication: Inhibition of the Cu (2+)-initiated oxidation of low-density lipoproteins. *Arzneimittelforschung*. 1994; 44:604–607.
210. Lau Benjamin HS. Suppression of LDL oxidation by garlic. *J Nutr*. 2001; 131:958S–988S.
211. Gebhardt R, Beck H. Differential inhibitory effects of garlic-derived organosulfur compounds on cholesterol biosynthesis in primary rat hepatocyte culture. *Lipids*. 1996; 31:1269–1276.
212. Rodger B, Roberty B, Edward S. Fibrinolytic activity in acute myocardial infarction. *Am J Clin Pathol*. 1972; 57:359–363.
213. Bordia A, Verma SK, Vyas AK, Khabya BL, Rathore AS, Bhu N, Bedi HK. Effect of essential oil of onion and garlic on experimental atherosclerosis in rabbits. *Atherosclerosis*. 1977; 26:379–386.
214. Bordia A, Arora SK, Kothari LK, Jain KC, Rathore BS, Rathore AS, Dube MK, Bhu N. The protective action of essential oils of onion and garlic in cholesterol-fed rabbits. *Atherosclerosis*. 1975; 22:103–109.
215. Sainani GS, Desai DB, Natu MN, Katrodia KM, Valame VP, Sainani PG. Onion, garlic,

- and experimental atherosclerosis. *Jpn Heart J.* 1979; 20:351–357.
216. Mirhadi SA, Singh S, Gupta PP. Effect of garlic supplementation to cholesterol-rich diet on the development of atherosclerosis in rabbits. *Ind J Exp Biol.* 1991; 29:162–168.
217. Bordia AK, Joshi HK, Sandhya YK, Bhu N. Effect of essential oil of garlic on serum fibrinolytic activity in patients with coronary artery disease. *Atherosclerosis.* 1977; 28:155.
218. Chutani SK, Bardia A. The effect of fried versus Raw garlic on fibrinolytic activity in man. *Atherosclerosis.* 1988; 38:417–421.
219. Sainani GS, Desai DB, Gorha NH, Natu SM, Pise DV, Sainani PG. Effect of dietary garlic and onion on serum lipid profile in Jain Community. *Ind J of Med Res.* 1979; 69:776–780.
220. Arora RC, Arora S, Gupta RK. The long-term use of garlic in ischemic heart disease. *Atherosclerosis.* 1981; 40:175–179.
221. Legnani C, Frascaro M, Guazzaloca G, Ludovici S, Cesarano G, Coccheri S. Effects of a dried garlic preparation on fibrinolysis and platelet aggregation in healthy subjects. *Arzneimittelforschung.* 1993; 43:119–122.
222. Bordia A, Verma SK, Srivastava KC. Effect of garlic (*Allium sativum*) on blood lipids, blood sugar, fibrinogen, and fibrinolytic activity in patients with coronary artery disease. *Prostaglandins Leukot Essent Fatty Acids.* 1998; 58:257–263.
223. Bordia AK, Sodhya SK, Rathore AS, Bhu N. Essential oil of garlic on blood lipids and fibrinolytic activity in patients with coronary artery disease. *J Assoc Phys Ind.* 1978; 26:327–33.
224. Bordia AK, Joshi HK. Garlic on fibrinolytic activity in cases of acute myocardial infarction. *J Assoc Physiol Ind.* 1978; 26:323–326.
225. Arora RC, Arora S. Comparative effects of clofibrate, garlic, and onion on alimentary hyperlipemia. *Atherosclerosis.* 1981; 39:447–452.
226. Bordia AK, Sharma KD, Parmar VK, Varma SK. Protective effect of garlic oil on the changes produced by 3 weeks of fatty diet on serum cholesterol serum triglycerides, fibrinolytic activity, and platelet adhesiveness in man. *Ind Heart J.* 1982; 34:86.
227. Harfenist WJ, Murry RK, Murry RK, Mayes PA, Grannen DK, Rodwell VW. Plasma proteins, immunoglobulin, and clotting factors. In: Barnes DA, editor. *Harper's Biochemistry.* 25. McGraw-Hill, New York, A Lange Medical Book; 2000. pp. 737–762
228. Ali M, Thomson M, Alnaqeeb MA, al-Hassan JM, Khater SH, Gomes A. Antithrombotic activity of garlic: its inhibition of the synthesis of thromboxane-B₂ during infusion of arachidonic acid and collagen in rabbits. *Prostaglandins Leukot Essent Fatty Acids.* 1990; 41:95–99.
229. Srivastava KC. Effects of aqueous extracts of onion, garlic, and ginger on platelet aggregation and metabolism of arachidonic acid in the blood vascular system: in vitro study. *Prostaglandins Leukot Med.* 1984; 13:227–235.
230. Ali M. Mechanism by which garlic (*Allium sativum*) inhibits cyclooxygenase activity. Effect of raw versus boiled garlic extract on the synthesis of prostanoids. *Prostaglandins Leukot Essent Fatty Acids.* 1995; 53:397–400.
231. Ali M, Bordia T, Mustafa T. Effect of raw versus boiled aqueous extract of garlic and onion on platelet aggregation. *Prostaglandins Leukot Essent Fatty Acids.* 1999; 60:43–47.
232. Laurence WVD, John DF. Garlic extract prevents acute platelet thrombus formation in

- stenosed canine coronary arteries. *Am Heart J.* 1989; 117:973–975.
233. Thomson M, Mustafa M, Ali M. Thromboxane-B (2) levels in serum of rabbits receiving a single intravenous dose of aqueous extract of garlic and onion. *Prostaglandins Leukot Essent Fatty Acids.* 2000; 63:217–221.
234. El-Sabban F, Fahim MA, Radwan GM, Zaghoul SS, and Singh S. Garlic preserves patency and delays hyperthermia-induced thrombosis in pial microcirculation. *Int J Hyperthermia.* 1996; 12:513–525.
235. El-Sabban F, Radwan GM. Influence of garlic compared to aspirin on induced photothrombosis in mouse pial microvessels, in vivo. *Thromb Res.* 1997; 88:193–203.
236. Apitz-Castro R, Escalante J, Vargas R, Jain MK. Ajoene, the antiplatelet principle of garlic, synergistically potentiates the antiaggregatory action of prostacyclin, forskolin, indomethacin, and dipyridamole on human platelets. *Thromb Res.* 1986; 42:303–311.
237. Apitz-Castro R, Badimon JJ, Badimon L. A garlic derivative, ajoene, inhibits platelet deposition on severely damaged vessel walls in an in vivo porcine experimental model. *Thromb Res.* 1994; 75:243–249.
238. Apitz-Castro R, Badimon JJ, Badimon L. Effect of ajoene, the major antiplatelet compound from garlic, on platelet thrombus formation. *Thromb Res.* 1992; 68:145–155.
239. Makheja AN, Bailey JM. Antiplatelet constituents of garlic and onion. *Agents Actions.* 1990; 29:360–363. Bordia A. Effect of garlic on human platelet aggregation in vitro. *Atherosclerosis.* 1978; 30:355–360.
240. Vanderhock JY, Makheja AN, Bailey JM. Inhibition of fatty acid oxygenases by onion and garlic acts. Evidence for the mechanism by which these oils inhibit platelet aggregation. *Biochem Pharmacol.* 1980; 29:3169–3173.
241. Srivastava KC. Evidence for the mechanism by which garlic inhibitors platelet aggregation. *Prostaglandin Leukot Med.* 1986; 22:313–321.
242. Samson RR. Effects of dietary garlic and temporal drift on platelet aggregation. *Atherosclerosis.* 1982; 44:119–120. Steiner M, Lin RS. Changes in platelet function and susceptibility of lipoproteins to oxidation associated with administration of aged garlic extract. *J Cardiovasc Pharmacol.* 1998; 31:904–908.
243. Boullin DJ. Garlic as a platelet inhibitor. *Lancet.* 1981; 1:776–777.
244. Ariga T, Oshiba S, Tamada T. Platelet aggregation inhibitor in garlic. *Lancet.* 1981; 1:150–151.
245. Apitz-Castro R, Cabrera S, Cruz MR, Ledezma E, Jain MK. Effects of garlic extract and three pure components isolated from it on human platelet aggregation, arachidonate metabolism, release activity, and platelet ultrastructure. *Thromb Res.* 1983; 32:155–169.
246. Block E, Ahmad S, Jain MK, Crecely RW, Apitz Castro R, Cruz MR. (E, Z) Ajoene: A potent antithrombic agent from garlic. *J Amer Chem Soc.* 1984; 106:8295–8296.
247. Harenberg J, Giese C, Zimmermann R. Effect of dried garlic on blood coagulation, fibrinolysis, platelet aggregation, and serum cholesterol levels in patients with hyperlipoproteinemia. *Atherosclerosis.* 1988; 74:247–249.
248. Kiesewetter H, Jung F, Pindur G, Jung EM, Mrowietz C, Wenzel E. Effect of garlic on thrombocyte aggregation, microcirculation, and other risk factors. *Int J Clin Pharmacol Ther Toxicol.* 1991; 29:151–155.

249. Kieseewetter H, Jung F, Jung EM, Mroweitz C, Koscielny J, Wenzel E. Effect of garlic on platelet aggregation in patients with increased risk of juvenile ischaemic attack. *Eur J Clin Pharmacol.* 1993; 45:333–336.
250. Morris J, Burke V, Mori TA, Vandongen R, Beilin LJ. Effects of garlic extract on platelet aggregation: a randomized placebo-controlled double-blind study. *Clin Exp Pharmacol Physiol.* 1995; 22:414–417.
251. Steiner M, Li W. Aged garlic extract, a modulator of cardiovascular risk factors: a dose-finding study on the effects of AGE on platelet functions. *J Nutr.* 2001; 131:980S–984S.
252. Wagner H, Wierer M, Fessler B. Effects of garlic constituents on arachidonate metabolism. *Planta Med.* 1987; 53:305–306.
253. Srivastava KC, Tyagi OD. Effects of a garlic-derived principle (ajoene) on aggregation and arachidonic acid metabolism in human blood platelets. *Prostaglandins Leukot Essent Fatty Acids.* 1993; 49:587–595.
254. Apitz-Castro R, Ledezma E, Escalante J, Jain MK. The molecular basis of the antiplatelet action of ajoene: direct interaction with the fibrinogen receptor. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun.* 1986; 141:145–150.
255. Jamaluddin MP, Krishnan LK, Thomas A. Ajoene inhibition of platelet aggregation: possible mediation by a hemoprotein. *Biochem Biophys Res Commun.* 1988; 153:479–486.
256. Schulz V, Hansel R, Tyler VE. *Rational Phytotherapy; Physicians' guide to herbal medicine.* Springer-verlag, Berlin;2001. Cardiovascular system. pp. 107–168.
257. Sial AY, Ahmed SJ. Study of the hypotensive action of garlic extract in experimental animals. *J Pak Med Assoc.* 1982; 32:237–239. Rashid A, Khan HH. The mechanism of hypotensive effect of garlic extract. *J Pak Med Assoc.* 1985; 35:357–362.
258. Chanderkar AG, Jain PK. Analysis of hypotensive action of *Allium sativum* (garlic). *Ind J Physiol Pharmacol.* 1973; 17:132–133.
259. Pantoja CV, Chiang Ch L, Norris BC, Concha JB. Diuretic, natriuretic, and hypotensive effects produced by *Allium sativum* (garlic) in anesthetized dogs. *J Ethnopharmacol.* 1991; 31:325–331. [PubMed] [Google Scholar] [Ref list] Banerjee AK. Effect of aqueous extract of garlic on arterial blood pressure of normotensive and hypertensive rats. *Artery.* 1976; 2:369.
260. Malik ZA, Siddiqui S. Hypotensive effect of freeze-dried garlic (*Allium sativum*) sap in the dog. *J Pak Med Assoc.* 1981; 31:12–13.
261. Elkayam A, Mirelman D, Peleg E, Wilchek M, Miron T, Rabinkov A, Sadetzki S, Rosenthal T. The effects of allicin and enalapril in fructose-induced hyperinsulinemic hyperlipidemic hypertensive rats. *Am J Hypertens.* 2001; 14:377–381.
262. Ali M, Al-Qattan KK, Al-Enezi F, Khanafer RM, Mustafa T. Effect of allicin from garlic powder on serum lipids and blood pressure in rats fed with a high cholesterol diet. *Prostaglandins Leukot Essent Fatty Acids.* 2000; 62:253–259.
263. Kaye AD, De Witt BJ, Anwar M, Smith DE, Feng CJ, Kadowitz PJ, Nossaman BD. Analysis of responses of garlic derivatives in the pulmonary vascular bed of the rat. *J Appl Physiol.* 2000; 89:353–358.
264. Al-Qattan KK, Khan I, Alnaqeeb MA, Ali M. Thromboxane-B₂, prostaglandin-E₂ and hypertension in the rat 2-kidney 1-clip model: a possible mechanism of the garlic induced hypotension. *Prostaglandins Leukot Essent Fatty Acids.* 2001; 64:5–10.

265. Kim-Park S, Ku DD. Garlic elicits a nitric oxide-dependent relaxation and inhibits hypoxic pulmonary vasoconstriction in rats. *Clin Exp Pharmacol Physiol.* 2000; 27:780–786.
266. Fallon MB, Abrams GA, Abdel-Razek TT, Dai J, Chen SJ, Chen YF, Luo B, Oparil S, and Ku DD. Garlic prevents hypoxic pulmonary hypertension in rats. *Am J Physiol.* 1998; 275:L283–L287.
267. Foushee DB, Ruffin J, Banerjee U. Garlic as a natural agent for the treatment of hypertension: A preliminary report. *Cytobios.* 1982; 34:145–152.
268. Brandle M, al Makdessi S, Weber RK, Dietz K, Jacob R. Prolongation of life span in hypertensive rats by dietary interventions. Effects of garlic and linseed oil. *Basic Res Cardiol.* 1997; 92:223–232.
269. Leoper M, DeBray M. Hypotensive effect of tincture of garlic. *Prog Med.* 1921; 36:391–392. Damru F. The use of garlic concentrate in vascular hypertension. *Med Rec.* 1941; 153:249–251.
270. Qidwai W, Qureshi R, Hasan SN, Azam SI. Effect of dietary garlic (*Allium Sativum*) on the blood pressure in humans – a pilot study. *J Pak Med Assoc.* 2000; 50:204–207.
271. Steiner M, Khan AH, Holbert D, Lin RI. A double-blind crossover study in moderately hypercholesterolemic men compared the effect of aged garlic extract and placebo administration on blood lipids. *Am J Clin Nutr.* 1996; 64:866–870.
272. Jain AK, Vargas R, Gotzkowsky S, McMahon FG. Can garlic reduce levels of serum lipids? A controlled clinical study. *Am J Med.* 1993; 94:632–635?
273. McMahon FG, Vargas R. Can garlic lower blood pressure? A pilot study. *Pharmacotherapy.* 1993; 13:406–407. Auer W, Eiber A, Hertkom E, Kohrle U, Lenz A, Mader F, Merx W, Otto G, Schmid-Oto B, benheim H. Hypertonie and Hyperlipidämie: In leichterenauch Knoblauch. *Der Allgemeinarzi.* 1989; 3:205–208.
274. Zimmermann W, Zimmermann B. Reduction in elevated blood lipids in hospitalized patients by a standardized garlic preparation. *Br J Clin Prac.* 1990; 44:20–23.
275. Vorberg G, Schneider B. Therapy with garlic: results of a placebo-controlled, double-blind study. *Br J Clin Prac.* 1990; 44:7–11.
276. Piotrowski'aillen GL. therapeutique. *Praxis.* 1948; 26:488–492.
277. König FK, Scineider B. Knoblauch bessert Durch-blutungstorungenArztliche Praxis. 1986. pp. 44–3.
278. Auer W, Eiber A, Hertkom E, Kohrle U, Lenz A, Mader F, Merx W, Otto G, Schmid-Oto B, benheim H. Hypertonie und Hyperlipidämie: In leichterenauch Knoblauch. *Der Allgemeinarzi.* 1989; 3:205–208. [Google Scholar] [Ref list] Petkov V. Plants and hypotensive, antiatheromatous and coronarodilatating action: *Am J Chin Med.* 1979; 7:197–236.
279. Zhejiang Institute of Traditional Chinese Medicine The effect of essential oil of garlic on hyperlipemia and platelet aggregation – an analysis of 308 cases. Cooperative Group for Essential Oil of Garlic. *J Tradit Chin Med.* 1986; 6:117–120.
280. Silagy CA, Neil HA. A meta-analysis of the effect of garlic on blood pressure. *J Hyperten.* 1994; 12:463–468.
281. Sendl A, Elbl G, Steinke B, Redl K, Breu W, Wagner H. Comparative pharmacological investigations of *Allium ursinum* and *Allium sativum*. *Planta Medica.* 1992; 58:1–7.
282. Granner DK, Murry RK, Mayes PA, Grannen DK, Rodwell VW. Hormones of the pancreas and gastrointestinal tract. In: Barnes DA, editor. *Harper's Biochemistry.* 25. McGraw-

- Hill, New York, A Lange Medical Book; 2000. pp. 610–626.
283. Ohaeri OC. Effect of garlic oil on the levels of various enzymes in the serum and tissue of streptozotocin-diabetic rats. *Biosci Rep.* 2001; 21:19–24.
284. Farva D, Goji LA, Joseph PK, Augusti KT. Effects of garlic oil on streptozotocin-diabetic rats maintained on normal and high-fat diets. *Indian J Biochem Biophys.* 1986; 23:24–27. Kumar GR, Reddy KP. Reduced nociceptive responses in mice with alloxan-induced hyperglycemia after garlic (*Allium Sativa*) treatment. *Indian J Exp Biol.* 1999; 37:662–666.
285. Mathew PT, Augusti KT. Studies on the effect of allicin (diallyl disulfide-oxide) on alloxan diabetes I. Hypoglycaemic action and enhancement of serum insulin effect and glycogen synthesis. *Indian J Biochem Biophys.* 1973; 10:209–212.
286. Kasuga S, Ushijima M, Morihara N, Itakura Y, Nakata Y. Effect of aged garlic extract (AGE) on hyperglycemia induced by immobilization stress in mice. *Nippon YakurigakuZassh.* 1999; 114:191–197.
287. Patumraj S, Tewit S, Amatyakul S, Jariyapongskul A, Maneesri S, Kasantikul V, Shepro D. Comparative effects of garlic and aspirin on diabetic cardiovascular complications. *Drug Deliv.* 2000; 7:91–96.
288. Sheela CG, Kumud K, Augusti KT. Anti-diabetic effect of onion and garlic sulfoxide amino acids in rats. *Planta Medica.* 1995; 61:356–357.
289. Sheela CG, Augusti KT. Antidiabetic effects of S-allyl cysteine sulphoxide isolated from garlic *Allium sativum* Linn. *Indian J Exp Biol.* 1992; 30:523–526.
290. Jain RC, Vyas CR. Garlic in alloxan-induced diabetic rabbits. *Am J Clin Nutr.* 1975; 28:684–685.
291. Augusti KT, Sheela CG. Antiperoxide effect of S-allyl cysteine sulfoxide, an insulin secretagogue, in diabetic rats. *Experientia.* 1996; 52:115–120.
292. Swanston-Flatt SK, Day C, Bailey CJ, Flatt PR. Traditional plant treatments for diabetes. Studies in normal and streptozotocin diabetic mice. *Diabetologia.* 1990; 33:462–464.
293. Jain RC, Vyas CR. Hypoglycemic action of onion and garlic. *Lancet.* 1973; 2:1491. Zhang XH, Lowe D, Giles P, Fell S, Connock MJ, Maslin DJ. Gender may affect the action of garlic oil on the plasma cholesterol and glucose levels of normal subjects. *J Nutr.* 2001; 131:1471–1478.
294. Ali M, Thomson M. Consumption of garlic clove a day could be beneficial in preventing thrombosis. *Prostaglandins Leukot Essent Fatty acids.* 1995; 53:211–212.
295. Li G, Shi Z, Jia H, Ju J, Wang X, Xia Z, Qin L, Ge C, Xu Y, Cheng L, Chen P, Yuan G. A clinical investigation on garlicinjection for treatment of unstable angina pectoris and its actions on plasma endothelin and blood sugar levels. *J Tradit Chin Med.* 2000; 20:243–246.
296. Rietz B, Belagyi J, Torok B, Jacob R. The radical scavenging ability of garlic examined in various models. *BolletinoChimicoFarmaceutico.* 1995; 134:69–76.
297. Martin N, Bardisa L, Pantojaa C, Vargas M, Quezaada P, Valenzuela J. Antiarrhythmic profile of a garlicdialystateassaay ed in dogs and isolated atrial preparations. *J Ethanopharmacol.* 1994; 43:1–8.
298. Martin N, Bardisa L, Pantojaa C, Vargas M, Quezaada P, Valenzuela J. Antiarrhythmic profile of a garlicdialystateassaay ed in dogs and isolated atrial preparations. *J Ethanopharmacol.* 1994; 43:1–8.
299. Aqel MB, Gharaibah MN, Salhab AS. Direct relaxant effects of garlic juice on smooth and

- cardiac muscles. *J Ethnopharmacol.* 1991; 33:13–19. Tongia SK. Effects of intravenous garlic Juice *Allium sativum* on rat Electrocardiogram. *Ind J PhysiolPharmacol.* 1984; 28:250–252.
300. Banerjee SK, Maulik M, Manchanda SC, Dinda AK, Gupta SK, Maulik SK. Dose-dependent induction of endogenous antioxidants in rat heart by chronic administration of garlic. *Life Sciences.* 2002; 70:1509–1518.
301. Banerjee SK, Maulik M, Manchanda SC, Dinda AK, Das TK, Maulik SK. Garlic-induced alteration in rat liver and kidney morphology and associated changes in endogenous antioxidant status. *Food Chem Toxicol.* 2001; 39:793–797.
302. Imai J, Ide N, Nagae S, Moriguchi T, Matsuura H, Itakura Y. Antioxidant and radical scavenging effects of aged garlic extract and its constituents. *Planta Med.* 1994; 60:417–420.
303. Geng Z, Lau B. Aged garlic extract modulates glutathione redox cycle and superoxide dismutase activity in vascular endothelial cells. *Phytother Res.* 1997; 11:54–56
304. Wei Z, Lau BHA. Garlic inhibits free radical generation and augments antioxidant enzyme activity in vascular endothelial cells. *Nutr Res.* 1998; 18:61–70.
305. Banerjee SK, Maulik M, Gupta SK, Manchanda SC, Dinda AK, Maulik SK. Effect of chronic garlic intake on endogenous antioxidants and ischemic-reperfusion injury in isolated rat heart. *Ind J Pharmacol.* 2001; 33:298 Mukherjee S, Maulik M, Talwar KK, Dinda AK, Maulik SK. Effect of chronic raw garlic administration in Adriamycin induced oxidant stress in rat hearts. *Ind J Pharmacol.* 2001; 33:297.
306. Kojima R, Epstein CJ, Mizui T, Carlson E, Chaqn PH. Protective effects of aged garlic extracts on doxorubicin-induced cardiotoxicity in the mouse. *Nutr Cancer.* 1994; 22:163–173.
307. Ciplea AG, Richter KD. The protective effect of *Allium sativum* and crataegus on isoprenaline-induced tissue necrosis in rats. *Arzneim-Forsch / Drug Res.* 1988; 38:1583–1592.
308. Isensee H, Rietz B, Jacob R. Cardioprotective action of garlic (*Allium sativum*). *Arzneim Forsch / Drug Res.* 1993; 43:94–98.
309. Yamasaki T, Lau BH. Garlic compounds protect vascular endothelial cells from oxidant injury. *Nippon YakurigakuZasshi.* 1997; 110:138P–141P.
310. Breithaupt-Grogler K, Belz GG. Epidemiology of the arterial stiffness. *Pathol Biol (Paris)* 1999; 47:604–6113] Breithaupt-Grogler K, Ling M, Boudoulas H, Belz GG. Protective effect of chronic garlic intake on elastic properties of aorta in the elderly. *Circulation.* 1997; 96:2649–2655.
311. Kiesewetter H, Jung F, Mrowietz C, Pindur G, Heiden M, Wenzel E, GU LD. Effects of garlic on blood fluidity and fibrinolytic activity: a randomized, placebo-controlled, double-blind study. *Br J Clin Pract.* 1990; 69:24–29.
312. Jung EM, Jung F, Mrowietz C, Kiesewetter H, Pindur G, Wenzel E. Influence of garlic powder on cutaneous microcirculation. A randomized placebo-controlled double-blind cross-over study in apparently healthy subjects. *Arzneimittelforschung.* 1991; 41:626–630.
313. Das T, Roychoudhury A, Sharma A, Talukder G. Effects of crude garlic extract on mouse chromosomes in vivo. *Food and Chemical Toxicology.* 1996; 34:43–47.
314. Augusti KT. Therapeutic values of onion (*Allium cepa* L) and garlic (*Allium sativum* L). *Ind J Exp Biol.* 1996; 34:634–640.

315. Nakagawa S, Masamoto K, Sumiyoshi H, Kunihiro K, Fuwa T. Effect of raw and extracted aged garlic on growth of young rats and their organ after peroral administration. *J Toxicol Sci.* 1980; 5:91–112.
316. Joseph PK, Rao KR, Sundaresh CS. Toxic effects of garlic extract and garlic oil in rats. *Ind J Exp Biol.* 1989; 27:977–979.
317. Chen L, Hong JY, So E, Hussain AH, Cheng WF. Decrease of hepatic catalase level by treatment with diallyl sulfide and garlic homogenates in rats and mice. *J Biochem Mol Toxicol.* 1999; 13:127–133.
318. Augusti KT, Mathew PT. Effect of allicin on certain enzymes of the liver after a short-term feeding to normal rats. *Experientia.* 1975; 31:148–149.
319. Dixit VP, Joshi S. Effects of chronic administration of garlic (*Allium sativum* Linn) on testicular function. *Ind J Exp Biol.* 1982; 20:534–536.
320. Egen-Schwind C, Eckard R, Kemper FH. Metabolism of garlic constituents in the isolated perfused rat liver. *Planta Medica.* 1992; 58:301–305.
321. Sheen LY, Li CK, Sheu SF, Meng RHC, Tsai SJ. Effect of the active principle of garlic-diallyl sulfide- on cell viability, detoxification capability, and the antioxidation system on primary rat hepatocytes. *Food Chem Toxicol.* 1996; 34:971–978.
322. Sheen LY, Chen HW, Kung YL, Liu CT, Lii CK. Effects of garlic oil and its organosulfur compounds on the activities of hepatic drug-metabolizing and antioxidant enzymes in rats fed high- and low-fat diets. *Nutr Cancer.* 1999; 35:160–166.
323. Gallwitz H, Bonse S, Martinez-Cruz A, Schlichting I, Schumacher K, Krauth-Siege RL. Ajoene is an inhibitor and subversive substrate of human glutathione reductase and *Trypanosoma cruzi* trypanothione reductase: crystallographic, kinetic, and spectroscopic studies. *J Med Chem.* 1999; 42:364–372.
324. Rabinkov A, Miron T, Mirelman D, Wilchek M, Glozman S, Yavin E, and Weiner L. S-Allylmercaptogluthathione: the reaction product of allicin with glutathione possesses SH-modifying and antioxidant properties. *Biochim BiophysActa.* 2000; 1499:144–153.
325. Beck E, Grunwald J. *Allium sativum* in der Stufentherapie der Hyperlipidämie. *Med Welt.* 1993; 44:516–520.
326. Koch HP, Hahn G, Lawson L, Reuter HD, Siegers CP. Garlic introduction to the therapeutic application of *Allium sativum* L. Williams & Wilkins, Baltimore, im Druck. 1995.
327. Eming SA, Piontek JO, Hunzelmann N, Rasokat H, Scharffetter-Kachanek K. Severe toxic contact dermatitis caused by garlic. *Br J Dermatol.* 1999; 141:391–392.
328. Falleroni AE, Zeiss CR, Levitz D. Occupational asthma secondary to inhalation of garlic dust. *J Allergy Clin Immunol.* 1981; 68:156–160.
329. Papageorgiou D, Corbet JP, Menezes F-Brando, Pecegueiro M, and Benezra C. Allergic: contact dermatitis to garlic (*Allium sativum* L) identification of the allergens: the role of mono-, di- and trisulfides present in garlic. *Arch Dermatol Res.* 1983; 275:229–234.
330. Rose KD, Croissant PD, Parliament CF, Levin MB. Spontaneous Spinal Epidural Hematoma with Associated Platelet Dysfunction from Excessive Garlic Ingestion: A Case Report. *Neurosurgery.* 1990; 26:880–882.
331. Petry JJ. Garlic and postoperative bleeding. *Plastic Recon Surg.* 1995; 96:483–484.

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